

\hbar Open Sets in μ_N Topological Spaces

Dr.N.Raksha Ben¹, Dr.E.Dulcy Jeba Mary²

^{1,2}PG and Research Department Of Mathematics,

Nazareth Margoschosis College at Pillaiyanmanai,

Nazareth-628617

Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti

Tirunelveli-627012, Tamilnadu,India

Abstract

In this article we have catechized about the traits of \hbar open sets in generalized topological spaces using Neutrosophic sets. Depending on the nature of \hbar open sets over the generalized topological spaces, some of its basic properties are contemplated.

Keywords: $\mu_N \hbar$ open set, $\mu_N \hbar$ int A , $\mu_N \hbar$ cl A

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1. Introduction

Smarandache proposed the novel postulations of neutrosophic sets from the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets[6][7]. Using neutrosophic crisp sets, A.A. Salama introduced Neutrosophic Topological Spaces[13]. The extension of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets, which address the degree of membership, the degree of indeterminacy, and the degree of non-membership of each component of X , are the neutrosophic sets. Later on 2020, G.Hari Siva Annam and N.Raksha Ben put forth the research on generalized topological spaces using neutrosophic sets[11]. Now, In this write up we launch a new initiatives to certain new forms of open sets in Generalized Topological Spaces using Neutrosophic sets. Also, we have evolved their closure, interior along with their attributes.

2. Preliminaries

Here, we bring back the ideas which are already exists in the field of neutrosophy.

Definition 2.1. A μ_N topology is a non - empty set X is a family of neutrosophic subsets in X satisfying the following axioms:

$$(\mu_{N_1})0_N \in \mu_N$$

$$(\mu_{N_2})G_1 \cup G_2 \in \mu_N \text{ for any } G_1, G_2 \in \mu_N.$$

Throughout this article, the pair of (X, μ_N) is known as μ_N Topological Space [μ_N TS for short].

Remark 2.2. A neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ can be identified to an ordered triple $A = \{ \langle \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle \}$ in $]^{-0}, 1^{+}[$ on X .

Remark 2.3. For the sake of simplicity, we shall use the symbol $A = \{ \langle \mu(x), \sigma(x), \gamma(x) \rangle \}$ for the neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$.

Example 2.4. Every intuitionistic fuzzy set A is a non empty set in X is obviously on Neutrosophic sets having the form $A = \{ \langle \mu_A(x), 1 - \mu_A(x) + \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$. In order to construct the tools for developing Neutrosophic Set and Neutrosophic topology, here we introduce the neutrosophic sets 0_N and 1_N in X as follows:

0_N may be defined as follows

$$(0_1)0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_2)0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_3)0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_4)0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

1_N may be defined as follows

$$(1_1)1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_2)1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_3)1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_4)1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Definition 2.5. Let $A = \{ \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle \}$ be a NS on X , then the complement of the set A [$C(A)$ for short] may be defined in three ways as follows:

$$(C_1)C(A) = \{ \langle x, 1 - \mu_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), 1 - \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(C_2)C(A) = \{ \langle x, \gamma_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(C_3)C(A) = \{ \langle x, \gamma_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Definition 2.6. Let X be a non-empty set and neutrosophic sets A and B in the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$. Then we may consider two possibilities for definitions for subsets ($A \subseteq B$).

$A \subseteq B$ may be defined as:

$$(A \subseteq B) \iff \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x), \forall x \in X$$

$$(A \subseteq B) \iff \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \geq \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x), \forall x \in X$$

Proposition 2.7. For any neutrosophic set A , the following conditions holds:
 $0_N \subseteq A, 0_N \subseteq 0_N, A \subseteq 1_N, 1_N \subseteq 1_N$.

Definition 2.8. Let X be a non empty set and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$, $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ are NSs. Then

(i) $A \cap B$ may be defined as:

$$(I_1) A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$$

$$(I_2) A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$$

(ii) $A \cup B$ may be defined as:

$$(I_1) A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$$

$$(I_2) A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$$

Definition 2.9. Let $\{A_j : j \in J\}$ be a arbitrary family of NSs in X , then

(i) $\cap A_j$ may be defined as:

$$\cap A_j = \langle x, \wedge_j \in J \mu_{A_j}(x), \wedge_j \in J \sigma_{A_j}(x), \vee_j \in J \gamma_{A_j}(x) \rangle$$

$$\cap A_j = \langle x, \wedge_j \in J \mu_{A_j}(x), \vee_j \in J \sigma_{A_j}(x), \vee_j \in J \gamma_{A_j}(x) \rangle$$

(ii) $\cup A_j$ may be defined as:

$$\cup A_j = \langle x, \vee_j \in J \mu_{A_j}(x), \vee_j \in J \sigma_{A_j}(x), \wedge_j \in J \gamma_{A_j}(x) \rangle$$

$$\cup A_j = \langle x, \vee_j \in J \mu_{A_j}(x), \wedge_j \in J \sigma_{A_j}(x), \wedge_j \in J \gamma_{A_j}(x) \rangle$$

Proposition 2.10. For all A and B are two neutrosophic sets then the following conditions are true:

$$C(A \cup B) = C(A) \cap C(B); C(A \cap B) = C(A) \cup C(B).$$

Definition 2.11. A neutrosophic topology [NT for Short] is a non-empty set X is a family τ_N of neutrosophic subsets in X satisfying the following axioms:

$$(NT_1) 0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$$

$$(NT_2) G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau_N \text{ for any } G_1, G_2 \in \tau_N$$

$$(NT_3) \cup G_i \in \tau_N \text{ for every } \{G_i : i \in J\} \subseteq \tau_N$$

The pair (X, τ_N) is called neutrosophic topological space [NTS for short]. The elements of τ_N are called neutrosophic open sets [NOS for short].

A neutrosophic set F is called neutrosophic closed if and only if $C(F)$ is neutrosophic open.

Definition 2.12. The complement of $A [C(A)]$ of NOS is called a neutrosophic closed set [NCS for short] in X .

Definition 2.13. Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N TS and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle \}$ be a neutrosophic set in X . Then the μ_N Closure is the intersection of all μ_N closed sets containing A .

Definition 2.14. Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N TS and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle \}$ be a neutrosophic set in X . Then the μ_N Interior is the union of all μ_N open sets contained in A .

Remark 2.15. * $\mu_N \text{int}(0_N) = 0_N$

$$* \mu_N \text{int}(1_N) \neq 1_N$$

$$* \mu_N \text{Int}(A) \subseteq A$$

$$* A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \mu_N \text{Int}A \subseteq \mu_N \text{Int}B$$

$$* \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Int}A) = \mu_N \text{Int}A$$

$$* \mu_N \text{Cl}(0_N) \neq 0_N$$

$$* \mu_N \text{Cl}(1_N) = 1_N$$

$$* A \subseteq \mu_N \text{Cl}(A)$$

$$* A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \mu_N \text{Cl}A \subseteq \mu_N \text{Cl}B$$

$$* \mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Cl}A) = \mu_N \text{Cl}A$$

3. μ_N^{\hbar} Open Sets

Definition 3.1. A subset δ of μ_N TS (X, μ_N) is said to be μ_N^{\hbar} open set if every non empty set U in $X, U \neq X$ and $U \in \mu_N$ such that $A \subseteq \mu_N \text{Int}(A \cup U)$. The complement of μ_N^{\hbar} open set is μ_N^{\hbar} closed. We denote the family of all μ_N^{\hbar} open sets of a μ_N TS (X, μ_N) by μ_N^{\hbar} .

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{a\}; \mu_N = \{0_N, A, C\}$ where $A = \langle 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 \rangle, B = \langle 0.3, 0.4, 0.6 \rangle, C = \langle 0.9, 0.7, 0.6 \rangle$. Here $\mu_N^{\hbar} = \{0_N, A, C\}$.

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{a\}; \mu_N = \{0_N, A, B, C\}$ where $A = \langle 0.3, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle, B = \langle 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, C = \langle 0.3, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, D = \langle 0.3, 0.6, 0.2 \rangle, E = \langle 0.3, 0.8, 0.5 \rangle$. Here the $\mu_N^{\hbar} = \{0_N, A, B, C, E\}$.

Remark 3.4. From example 3.2 and 3.3 it is observed that $\mu_N \subseteq \mu_N^{\hbar}$

Theorem 3.5. *Every μ_N open set is $\mu_N\hbar$ Open.*

Proof. Let ζ be a μ_N open set in X which implies us that $\mu_N\text{Int}\zeta = \zeta$. Hence, we get $\zeta = \mu_N\text{Int}(\zeta) \subseteq \mu_N\text{Int}(\zeta \cup U)$ for any non empty set $U \neq X$ and $U \in \mu_N$. Thus, $U \subseteq \mu_N\text{Int}(\zeta \cup U)$. Hence, it is $\mu_N\hbar$ Open. \square

Remark 3.6. *Converse of the theorem need not be true.*

Example 3.7. Let $X = \{a\}$; $\mu_N = \{0_N, \lambda, \xi, \varrho, \nu, \vartheta\}$ where $\lambda = \langle 0.3, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle$, $\xi = \langle 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$, $\varrho = \langle 0.3, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$, $\nu = \langle 0.3, 0.6, 0.2 \rangle$, $\vartheta = \langle 0.3, 0.8, 0.5 \rangle$. Here, The $\mu_N\hbar$ open sets are $\{0_N, \lambda, \xi, \varrho, \vartheta, \lambda^c, \xi^c, \varrho^c, \nu^c, 1_N\}$ which tell us that ϑ is $\mu_N\hbar$ open but it is not μ_N open set.

Definition 3.8. Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N Topological Space and let $A \subseteq X$. The $A \subseteq X$ interior is defined as the union of all $\mu_N\hbar$ open sets contained in A and it is denoted by $\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(A)$. It is clear that $\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(A)$ is $\mu_N\hbar$ open set for any subset A of X .

Proposition 3.9. Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N Topological Space and let $A \subseteq B \subseteq X$. Then

- * $\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(A) \subseteq \mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(B)$
- * $\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(A)\hbar A$
- * A is $\mu_N\hbar$ open if and only $A = \mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(A)$

Result 3.10. $\blacktriangleright \mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(0_N) = 0_N$

$\blacktriangleright \mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(1_N) \neq 1_N$

Definition 3.11. Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N Topological Space and let $A \subseteq X$. The $A \subseteq X$ closure is defined as the union of all $\mu_N\hbar$ open sets containing A and it is denoted by $\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Cl}(A)$. It is clear that $\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Cl}(A)$ is $\mu_N\hbar$ closed set for any subset A of X .

Result 3.12. $\blacktriangleright \mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Cl}(0_N) \neq 0_N$

$\blacktriangleright \mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Cl}(1_N) = 1_N$

Theorem 3.13. Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N Topological Space then the following statements hold:

- a) $\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Cl}(C(A)) = C(\mu_N\text{Int}(A))$.
- b) $\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(C(A)) = C(\mu_N\text{Cl}(A))$.
- c) $C(\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Cl}(C(A))) = \mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(A)$.
- d) $C(\mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Int}(C(A))) = \mu_N^{\hbar}\text{Cl}(A)$.

Proof. a) Let $x \in \mu_N^h Cl(C(A))$ then $x \in \cap F$, F is μ_N^h closed sets and $C(A) \subseteq F$ which yields that $x \in F$, for each μ_N^h closed sets F such that $C(A) \subseteq F$. Hence, we get $x \notin X - F$ for all μ_N^h open sets $X - F$ such that $X - F \subseteq A$. Then $x \notin \mu_N^h Int(A)$. Hence $X \in C(\mu_N^h Int(A)) \rightarrow \mu_N^h Cl(C(A)) \subseteq C(\mu_N^h Int(A))$.

Suppose $x \notin \mu_N^h Cl(C(A)) \rightarrow x \notin \cap F$, F is μ_N^h closed sets and $C(A) \subseteq F$ which implies that $x \notin F$, for some μ_N^h closed sets contains $C(A)$. Therefore, $x \in X - F$ for some μ_N^h open set $X - F$ such that $X - F \subseteq A$ and hence $x \in \mu_N^h Int(A)$ which implies that $x \notin C(\mu_N^h Int(A))$. Henceforth, $C(\mu_N^h Int(A)) \subseteq \mu_N^h Cl(C(A))$. Hence we get $\mu_N^h Cl(C(A)) = C(\mu_N^h Int(A))$.

b) The proof is similar to a).

c) The proof follows by taking complement in a).

d) The proof can be implemented by replacing A by \bar{A} in a). □

Definition 3.14. If $\mu_N^h Ext(A) = \mu_N^h Int(C(A))$ then it will be called as μ_N Exterior of A .

Result 3.15. (i) $\mu_N^h Ext(1_N) = 0_N$

(ii) $\mu_N^h Ext(0_N) \neq 1_N$

Proof. (i) $\mu_N^h Ext(1_N) = \mu_N^h Int(C(1_N)) = \mu_N^h Int(0_N) = 0_N$.

(ii) $\mu_N^h Ext(0_N) = \mu_N^h Int(C(0_N)) = \mu_N^h Int(1_N) \neq 1_N$. □

Theorem 3.16. $\mu_N^h Ext(A) = C(\mu_N^h Cl(A))$

Proof. $\mu_N^h Ext(A) = \mu_N^h Int(C(A)) = \mu_N^h Int(X - A) = X - \mu_N^h Cl(A) = C(\mu_N^h Cl(A))$. □

Theorem 3.17. $\mu_N^h Ext(A \cup B) \subseteq \mu_N^h Ext(A) \cap \mu_N^h Ext(B)$

Proof. $\mu_N^h Ext(A \cup B) = \mu_N^h Int(C(A \cup B)) = \mu_N^h Int(C(A) \cap C(B)) \subseteq \mu_N^h IntC(A) \cap \mu_N^h IntC(B) = \mu_N^h Ext(A) \cap \mu_N^h Ext(B)$. □

Theorem 3.18. $\mu_N^h Ext(A \cap B) = \mu_N^h Ext(A) \cup \mu_N^h Ext(B)$.

Proof. $\mu_N^h Ext(A \cap B) = \mu_N^h Int(C(A \cap B)) \supseteq \mu_N^h Int(C(A) \cup C(B)) = \mu_N^h Int(C(A)) \cup \mu_N^h Int(C(B)) = \mu_N^h Ext(A) \cup \mu_N^h Ext(B)$. □

Theorem 3.19. $\mu_N^h Ext(\mu_N^h Ext(A)) = \mu_N^h Int(\mu_N^h Cl(A)) \supseteq \mu_N^h Int(A)$.

Proof. $\mu_N^h Ext(\mu_N^h Ext(A)) = \mu_N^h Ext(\mu_N^h Int(C(A))) = \mu_N^h IntC(\mu_N^h Int(C(A))) = \mu_N^h Int(\mu_N^h Cl(A)) \supseteq \mu_N^h Int(A)$. □

Theorem 3.20. If $A \subseteq B$, then $\mu_N^h Ext(B) \subseteq \mu_N^h Ext(A)$.

Proof. Suppose $A \subseteq B$, then $\mu_N^h Ext(B) = \mu_N^h Int(C(B)) \subseteq \mu_N^h Int(C(A)) = \mu_N^h Ext(A)$. \square

Definition 3.21. If A is a neutrosophic subset of μ_N Topological space X then μ_N^h Frontier of A is defined as $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap \mu_N^h Cl(C(A))$.

Remark 3.22. If A is a neutrosophic subset of μ_N Topological space X then μ_N^h Frontier of A is always closed.

Theorem 3.23. If A is a μ_N^h open subset of μ_N Topological space X then $A \setminus \mu_N^h Fr(A) \subseteq A$.

Proof. Since A is μ_N^h open, $C(A)$ is μ_N^h closed. We have $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap \mu_N^h Cl(C(A)) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap C(A)$. Now $C(\mu_N^h Fr(A)) = C(\mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap (C(A))) = C(\mu_N^h Cl(A)) \cup C(C(A)) = C(\mu_N^h Cl(A)) \cup A$. Now $A \setminus \mu_N^h Fr(A) = A \cap C(\mu_N^h Fr(A)) = A \cap (C(\mu_N^h Cl(A)) \cup A) = (A \cap C(\mu_N^h Cl(A))) \cup (A \cup A) \subseteq (A \cap C(A)) \cup A = \varphi \cup A = A$. \square

Theorem 3.24. If A is a not a μ_N^h open subset of μ_N Topological space X then $A \setminus \mu_N^h Fr(A) \subseteq A$.

Proof. $A \setminus \mu_N^h Fr(A) = A \cap (C(\mu_N^h Fr(A)))$ which implies that $A \cap U \subseteq A$ where $U = C(\mu_N^h Fr(A))$ which is μ_N^h open since by remark 3.21. Hence, $A \setminus \mu_N^h Fr(A) \subseteq A$. \square

Theorem 3.25. If A is a neutrosophic subset of μ_N Topological space X then $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Fr(C(A))$.

Proof. $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap \mu_N^h Cl(C(A)) = \mu_N^h Cl(X \setminus A) \cap \mu_N^h Cl(X \setminus C(A)) = \mu_N^h Fr(C(A))$. \square

Theorem 3.26. Let A be a neutrosophic subsets of μ_N Topological space X then $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) - \mu_N^h Int(A)$.

Proof. By Theorem 3.12, we have $C(\mu_N^h Cl(C(A))) = \mu_N^h IntA$ and by the definition of $\mu_N^h Fr(A)$, $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap \mu_N^h Cl(C(A))$ which is equivalent to $\mu_N^h Cl(A) - C(\mu_N^h Cl(C(A)))$ since we have $A - B = A \cap C(B)$. Thus, $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) - \mu_N^h Int(A)$. \square

Theorem 3.27. Let A be a neutrosophic subsets of μ_N Topological space X then $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) - \mu_N^h Int(A)$.

Proof. By Theorem 3.12, we have $C(\mu_N^h Cl(C(A))) = \mu_N^h Int A$ and by the definition of $\mu_N^h Fr(A)$, $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap \mu_N^h Cl(C(A))$ which is equivalent to $\mu_N^h Cl(A) - C(\mu_N^h Cl(C(A)))$ since we have $A - B = A \cap C(B)$. Thus, $\mu_N^h Fr(A) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) - \mu_N^h Int(A)$. \square

Theorem 3.28. For each $A \in \mu_N TS(X)$, $A \cup \mu_N^h Fr(A) \subseteq \mu_N^h Cl(A)$.

Proof. Let A be a neutrosophic subsets of μ_N Topological space X . $A \cup \mu_N^h Fr(A) = A \cup (\mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap \mu_N^h Cl(C(A))) (A \cup (\mu_N^h Cl(A))) \cap (A \cup (\mu_N^h Cl(C(A)))) = \mu_N^h Cl(A) \cap (A \cup (\mu_N^h Cl(C(A)))) \subseteq \mu_N^h Cl(A)$. \square

4. Conclusion

In this article, we have discussed μ_N^h open sets some characterizations of μ_N^h open sets in μ_N Topological Spaces. Some important nature of μ_N^h open sets were discussed. Later on many properties such as μ_N^h connected, μ_N^h compact and μ_N^h continuous will be discovered.

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